

CESSDA in ERA

collaborations, partnerships and perspectives

8 June 2022, IASSIST Conference 2022

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MISSION

to provide a full-scale sustainable research infrastructure that enables the research community to conduct high-quality research in the social sciences which can contribute to effective solutions to the major challenges facing society today.

Membership

1. Austria
2. Belgium
3. Croatia
4. Czech Republic
5. Denmark
6. Finland
7. France
8. Germany
9. Greece
10. Hungary
11. Iceland
12. Ireland
13. North Macedonia
14. Netherlands
15. Norway
16. Portugal
17. Serbia
18. Slovak Republic
19. Slovenia
20. Sweden
21. Switzerland (Observer)
22. UK
23. Italy

Countries aiming at membership:

- Bosnia and Herzegovina
- Bulgaria
- Estonia
- Lithuania
- Poland
- Romania
- Spain

Timeline

ESFRI Roadmap

SOCIAL & CULTURAL INNOVATION / LANDMARK

CESSDA ERIC

Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives

SOCIAL & CULTURAL INNOVATION / LANDMARK

CLARIN ERIC

Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure

SOCIAL & CULTURAL INNOVATION / LANDMARK

DARIAH ERIC

Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities

SOCIAL & CULTURAL INNOVATION / LANDMARK

ESS ERIC

European Social Survey

SOCIAL & CULTURAL INNOVATION / LANDMARK

SHARE ERIC

Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe

CESSDA ERIC

Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives

GENERAL INFO

Website

<http://www.cessda.eu>

Headquarters

CESSDA ERIC
Bergen, Norway

Legal Status

ERIC, 2017

Type

distributed

DESCRIPTION

The Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA) is a distributed Research Infrastructures serving as a large-scale, integrated and sustainable platform for data services relevant to the Social Sciences. It supports high-quality, national and international research and cooperation by bringing together Social Science data archives across Europe, and expand easy access to data and metadata regardless of borders. CESSDA is aiming at facilitating social, economic and political research, thus contributing to the production of effective solutions to the major challenges facing society today. CESSDA supports continuous learning and training of its data providers and user community to cover research data management, data discovery and reuse, digital preservation and data archiving.

Since its establishment in 1976, CESSDA served as an informal umbrella organisation for European national Social Science data archives. In the ESFRI Roadmap since 2006, CESSDA has been listed as success story in the Roadmap 2010 and was recognised as ESFRI Landmarks in 2016. It became a legal institution limited company under Norwegian law (CESSDA AS) in 2013 and then an European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) in 2017. Norway is hosting CESSDA, and the main office is located in Bergen. Presently 16 countries are Members of the Consortium and one country is a formal Observer, each represented by a national institution providing relevant services. Additionally, Social Science data archives from other European countries are cooperating, taking part to some activities or aiming at membership.

TIMELINE & ESTIMATED COSTS

INTERCONNECTIONS

POLITICAL SUPPORT

- Lead**
NO
- Member**
AT, BE, CZ, DE, DK, EL, FI, FR, HR, HU, IE, IS, IT, MK, NL, PT, RS, SE, SI, SK, UK
- Observer**
CH

European Research Area

An ERA Policy Agenda with concrete actions

The new ERA Policy Agenda, annexed to the Council conclusions on the ERA governance, sets out 20 concrete ERA actions for the period 2022-2024 to contribute to the priority areas defined in the Pact for Research and Innovation.

- 1. Enable Open Science, including through the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)**
- Propose an EU copyright and data legislative framework for research
- Reform the Assessment System for research, researchers and institutions
- Promote attractive research careers, talent circulation and mobility
- Promote gender equality and foster inclusiveness
- Protect academic freedom in Europe
- Upgrade EU guidance for a better knowledge valorisation
- 8. Strengthen research infrastructures**
- 9. Promote international cooperation**
- Make EU research and innovation missions and partnerships key contributors to the ERA
- An ERA for green transformation
- Accelerate the green/digital transition of Europe's key industrial ecosystems
- Empower Higher Education Institutions
- 14. Bring Science closer to citizens**
- 15. Build-up research and innovation ecosystems to improve excellence and competitiveness**
- 16. Improve EU-wide access to excellence**
- Enhance public research institutions' strategic capacity
- Support the development of EU countries' national processes for the ERA implementation
- Establish an ERA monitoring system
- Support research and innovation investments and reforms

The New European Research Area

Joining forces to find solutions to today's challenges is more important than ever. Working together through the new European Research Area, we will accelerate our transition towards climate neutrality and digital leadership, support the recovery from the coronavirus crisis and make the EU a lighthouse of excellence for research and innovation.

Mariya Gabriel, Commissioner for Innovation, Research, Culture, Education and Youth

What is the European Research Area?

- A single, borderless market for research, innovation and technology across the EU...
- ...where countries come together and improve their research policies and systems...
- ...and where there is free movement of researchers, knowledge and innovation.

In the new European Research Area we will:

- Prioritise investments and reforms in research and innovation** towards the green and digital transition, to support Europe's recovery;
- Strengthen mobility of researchers and free flow of knowledge and technology** through greater cooperation among Member States;
- Boost market uptake** of research and innovation results;
- Improve access to excellence** for researchers across the EU.

Research and Innovation

European Research Infrastructures advancing the European Open Science Cloud

Social Scientific Communities advancing Social Scientific Research

European Research Infrastructures advancing the Digital Future of Europe

Advancing the SSH Research

Vanja Komljenovic

Dimitra Kondyli

 cessda.eu

 @CESSDA_Data

Starting point

European level - current connections

Assets for research work

Training

Learn how to discover, use, manage and preserve research data

Upcoming Events

Tue 7 Jun 2022 - Fri 10 Jun 2022
IASSIST 2022 – Data by Design: Building a Sustainable Data Culture
The conference theme, "Data by Design: Building a Sustainable Data Culture", emphasizes two cor...

Thu 9 Jun 2022
Webinar on European Research Data Landscape study findings
A team of Visionary Analytics, DANS, DCC and EFIS is carrying out a study on the European Resea...

[Event Calendar](#) →

Featured Resources

The [Data Management Expert Guide \(DMEG\)](#) is a comprehensive guide to Research Data Management and FAIR data principles.

[Data Management Expert Guide](#)

The [Data Archiving Guide \(DAG\)](#) is designed to provide new employees at social science data archives with a general understanding of the work a data archive performs.

[Data Archiving Guide](#)

Trust and Standards

Each national Service Provider works towards achieving the Trustworthy Digital Repository (TDR) standard selected by CESSDA: the [CoreTrustSeal](#).

The CoreTrustSeal defines repository requirements in terms of organisational infrastructure, digital object management, technology and security. Trust is essential between CESSDA Service Providers and with their data depositors and users.

Since CESSDA selected the internationally recognised CoreTrustSeal it has been acknowledged as important for enabling FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data and has become the recommended certification approach for data repositories within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

Service Providers with experience of trust standards and certification form the Trust Group, and every CESSDA member and aspiring member has a key contact to represent them on trust issues.

To date more than half of Service Providers have achieved certification and have entered the three year renewal cycle of reassessment. CESSDA work on trust continues to guide and support these repositories and more recent CESSDA members on a range of issues and standards relating to trusted data and services.

CESSDA Digital Tools

CESSDA Data Catalogue

Search tens of thousands of social science research studies from our European Service Providers.

ELSST Thesaurus

The European Language Social Science Thesaurus is a broad-based multilingual thesaurus for the social sciences.

European Question Bank

The EQB is a cross-national question bank for social science and humanities research.

Vocabulary Service

Search, browse and download controlled vocabularies in a variety of languages.

Resource Directory

Access resources for data archives and data professionals from CESSDA, its Service Providers and partners.

Metadata Validator

Validate metadata for compatibility with the CESSDA Data Catalogue and the European Question Bank.

Assets for research work

The banner features a dark blue background with several images: a network graph, an aerial view of a village, a person working at a computer, a wind turbine, solar panels, and a candlestick chart. The text is white and blue.

cessda
DC Data Catalogue

CESSDA Data Search and Discovery

Empowering European Social Science Research

General numbers:
>**30.000** Datasets
>**20** European Social Science Data Archives
Collections from **1900-now**
Contributing to tackling **5** global challenges

SEARCH BY:

TOPIC COLLECTION YEARS COUNTRY PUBLISHER LANGUAGE OF DATA FILES

CESSDA Data Catalogue

<https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/>

- one - stop - shop for search and discovery
- metadata of the study level
- data holdings of CESSDA 's Service Providers
- over 35,000 datasets from European Social Science Data Archives
- covering collections back to 1900

Assets for research work

ABOUT NEWS & EVENTS CONTACT COVID-19 TOOLS & SERVICES TRAINING DATA CATALOGUE

Home / Covid-19

CESSDA and COVID-19

CESSDA and its national [Service Providers](#) strive to serve the research community despite the coronavirus crisis, and online services continue to function as usual. The CESSDA consortium is especially committed to supporting researchers working on COVID-19 related research.

On this page you can find information about COVID-19 specific resources from the CESSDA consortium and other relevant sources.

Research communities, projects and opportunities

Migration is a topic that remains high on the EC agenda and consequently on the researchers' interests across Europe and worldwide.

HumMingBird (2019-2023) is a Horizon 2020 project <https://hummingbird-h2020.eu/>

16 partners across Europe aiming at improving understanding of dynamics of migration flows and their drivers by analysing patterns, motivations, geographical routes' changes, etc., using mixed data techniques, new data types and sources as well as more traditional quantitative and qualitative data sources.

CESSDA's role is to ensure that collected data feeds in the CESSDA Data Catalogue, ensuring FAIR, render accessible to a large variety of stakeholders (designated research communities, potential interested policy makers, and the wider public with the post-project exploitation of data and indicators).

BY-COVID creates a **multidisciplinary data ecosystem** for COVID-19 which will help enhance pandemic preparedness.

53 partners bring together data resources and catalogues across domains, captures data governance and access procedures.

Engage with national and international stakeholders, train and build capacity of national and international stakeholders.

CESSDA' role is to connect Fair SS data by widening the portal scope from molecular to population focus , train SS researchers and interact at an extent with life sciences researchers, work on an interdisciplinary perspective with regard to open metadata and possible restricted data.

A pioneer project, an explorative cooperation to respond to constantly transforming societal challenges by responsible and interdisciplinary research

Connecting - cooperating

- CESSDA ERIC explores collaborations, defines its position at the EU and global scale.
- CESSDA is strengthening its position by connecting with thematic research communities.
- Widening and outreach across scientific domains.
- Exploring and experimenting new data types, data landscape and research communities.

To learn more, we invite you to attend:

Wednesday, 8 June 2022

Session C2: Partnerships and collaborations

15:30-17:00 PM

(Virtual) - Moving with the times: multilingual thesaurus management in a changing environment

Thursday, 9 June 2022

Panel 3: Training as grounds for collaboration across disciplinary boundaries

15:30-17:00 PM

Session D1: Data access, governance and ethics

15:30-17:00 PM

(Virtual) - Managing data access in CESSDA I: the Data Catalogue and Beyond

(Virtual) - Managing data access in CESSDA II: the Data Access Policy

Thursday, 9 June 2022

Panel 5: The CESSDA Data Archives joint efforts to support journals in data sharing and reproducibility

15:30-17:00 PM

Friday, 10 June 2022

Data Services of the future

11:00-12:30

Panel 7: Trust Standards, Support and FAIR Enabling Trustworthy Repositories

Advancing the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

Martina Drascic Capar

Carsten Thiel

 cessda.eu

 @CESSDA_Data

CESSDA participating in building EOSC

"Web of FAIR Data and services' for science in Europe. EOSC will be a multi-disciplinary environment where researchers can publish, find and re-use data, tools and services, enabling them to better conduct their work."

European Strategy of Data

5 cluster projects to build EOSC

ESFRI cluster projects - Position papers on expected contributions to the EOSC

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) initiative already has a high level of data and with the current funding by the European Commission of interdisciplinary exploitation of data can only improve. The future EOSC detailed in close collaboration between the EOSC governance board and EOSCsecretariat.eu is undertaking pooling of stakeholder views on document presents a collection of five position papers from ESFRI clusters. The ESFRI cluster projects were launched in 2019 in order to implement and data management solutions, to create cross-border and open science clouds via the EOSC portal for a larger user community.

ESFRI Science Clusters Position Statement on Expectations and Long-Term Commitment in Open Science

The Science Cluster (ENVRI-FAIR, EOSC-Life, ESCAPE, PANOSC and SSHOC) delivered a new position paper with a formal explanation of the urgent need of EC to support a longer-term role of the five Science Clusters to provide content to the EOSC, to enhance researchers' involvement in Open Science and to suggest potential cooperative pathways in the Horizon-Europe framework and along with the EOSC Association roadmap.

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RIS,

SSHOC
social sciences & humanities open cloud

Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

Partners: 53

(28 beneficiaries + 25 LTPs)

SSH ESFRI Landmarks and Projects
& international SSH data infrastructures

Project budget:
€ 14,5 MIL

Type of action & funding:
Research and Innovation action
(INFRAEOSC-04-2018)

Project website:
www.SSHOpenCloud.eu

Duration: 40 months
(January 2019 – 30 April 2022)

Objectives:

- creating the social sciences and humanities (**SSH**) part of European Open Science Cloud (**EOSC**)
- maximising **reuse** through **Open Science** and **FAIR** principles (**standards, common catalogue, access control, semantic techniques, training**)
- interconnecting existing and new infrastructures (**clustered cloud infrastructure**)
- establishing appropriate **governance model** for SSH-EOSC

SSHOC Highlights

SSH Open Marketplace up & running, one-stop access for SSH resources, tools and services, workflows on how to use them & suggestions for similar tools

SSHOC website - main communication channel and gateway to services (Marketplace)

Regular coordination and alignment with other Cluster projects (EOSC-Life, ESCAPE, ENVRI-FAIR and PANOSC)

6 ESFRIs (5 Landmarks, 1 project) working together

Social media community of 2200+ members, and 470 newsletter subscribers

5000+ stakeholders engaged in 100+ events

7 onboarded SSH data communities, SSH Marketplace testers' community, SSH Training community - 172 members

6 Services onboarded on EOSC, 7 in process, 3 pending

100+ official reports, 33 KERs

(SSH Open Marketplace system specifications downloaded over 4300 times)

SSHOC Results

33 SSHOCing Key Exploitable Results to support your research in SSH and Beyond

<https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/>

SSH OPEN MARKETPLACE
 FAIR SSH data citation prototype
 API for Generations and Gender Programme (GGP)
 Archive in a Box (Dataverse)
 SSH GDPR Code of Conduct
 CLARIN Switchboard
 Virtual Collection Registry
 SSH Conversion Hub
 Web Panel Sample Service (WPSS) for cross-national surveys and panels
 Audio Survey Experiment
 Cultural heritage Aioli-platform
 Framework for data use agreement
 SSH Trainer's Directory
 SSH Training Discovery Toolkit
 [MCSQ]: The Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires
 Improved and FAIR data Repositories - SSHOC Trusted Repositories (SSHOC Trust Support)
 Ethnic and Migrant Minority Survey Registry
 Automatic Verification Tool
 Knowledge Graphs in Electoral Studies to bring together structured and unstructured data
 surveycodings.org
 SSHOCro
 RESTORE
 ARIADNE-plus
 League of Data
 ADS Guides to Good Practice
 Multilingual Terminologies
 Improved and FAIR data Repositories - New ESS data repository
 Improved and FAIR data Repositories - SHARE survey data
 Dataset: investigating the effects of machine translation and post-editing in survey translation
 SSH Training Community
 6 data Communities

- available for further research activities after the end of the project
- covering data management, sharing & discovery, training & support, processing & analysis and SSH Communities
- all tools are being made accessible via **the SSH Open Marketplace** and 13 of them **onboarded on EOSC Portal**

What is in it for me?

SSHOC League of Data Game

- Play it at: <https://lod.sshopencloud.eu>
- Pilot tool based on 2 out of 7 chapters of **CESSDA DMEG®** (Data management Expert Guide)

SSHOC'n Tell Challenge
User Story

League of Data as a teaser for a data management training

View the presentation

Trying out

Ellen Leenarts
DANS

What
When inviting data supporters and researchers for a data management training, it would be great if we could make them aware of basic knowledge around archiving and publishing research data and the overview presented in the Data Management Expert Guide. For this purpose I will have a closer look at the League of Data game. Basically the game should be fun and not raise questions, but already show how a researcher profits from data management. It is very relevant for my daily work as I am involved in organising training events.

Who
I'm coordinator Training and Consultancy at the Data Archiving and Management Expert Guide for CESSDA.

How
Play the LoD game and focus on: how straightforward it is to play, with management, archiving and publishing. It would be best if I could test that option might be available in a couple of weeks. The issue he think we should not take it too serious, just a manner to steer them to the Guide.

When
The plan is to integrate the LoD game as a teaser to some of our training events.

Try the Game

SSHOC Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud
Union's Horizon 2020 project call H2020-INFRAEOSC4

Home The game SSHOC LOD DMEG Contact

Data publication challenge

DATA MANAGEMENT CHALLENGE

Play now

SSH Training Discovery Toolkit

- <https://training-toolkit.sshopencloud.eu/>
- inventory of training materials relevant for the SSH

SSHOpenCluster Social Sciences & Humanities Resources SSH Training Discovery Toolkit

About Privacy policy Legal notice Contact

The SSH Training Discovery Toolkit provides an inventory of training materials relevant for the Social Sciences and Humanities. Use the search bar to discover materials or browse through the collections. The filters will help you identify your area of interest.

Search for sources and items Search

Search entities

Displaying 1 - 100 of 100

Source	Description	Organisation
Alison	Alison is one of the world's largest free learning platforms for education and skills training.	Alison
ALLEA Events & Publications	ALLEA regularly produces a wide range of scientific and science-policy publications and recommendations, webinars and events responding to on-going issues and de	ALLEA
Australian Research Data Commons Training Materials	The ARDC is a transformational initiative that enables Australian research community and industry access to nationally significant, leading edge data intensive infrastructure, platforms, skills an	The Australian Research Data Commons
Belmont Forum e-Infrastructures & Data Management Toolkit	This repository contains resources (links to training, policies, best practices, and other information) that enable Belmont Forum researchers to meet the Data Ma	Belmont Forum

Entity type

- Item (259)
- Source (100)

Organisation

- 4TU.ResearchData (1)
- Academy of Athens (1)
- Alison (1)
- ALLEA (1)
- ANT Foundation Italy Onlus (1)
- Association of European Research Libraries (3)
- Australasia Preserves (1)
- Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage (1)
- Babraham Institute (1)
- Belmont Forum (1)

Show more

SSH Open Cluster

From SSHOC to the SSH Open Cluster

Breaking down community silos to advance Social Science and Humanities Research

Memorandum of Understanding for the establishment of the SSH Open Cluster

PREAMBLE

The Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) ESFRI Landmarks and Projects, as well as relevant international SSH data infrastructures and other stakeholders gathered in the Horizon 2020 project Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) want to preserve SSHOC project's numerous outputs, make them sustainable, and exploitable.

The aim of the SSHOC project was to create a European open cloud ecosystem for social sciences and humanities, consisting of technical and social components, to maximise re-use of SSH data through Open Science and FAIR principles, to interconnect existing and new SSH infrastructures, and to establish the governance for the SSH part of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

The undersigned European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs):

- Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA),
- Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure (CLARIN),
- Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH),
- European Social Survey (ESS), and
- Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE).

hereinafter referred to as the Parties and acting as the founding members, have hereby agreed as follows:

Article 1. Scope and Objectives of the MoU

The overall objective of this MoU is to prepare the establishment of the SSH Open Cluster to further intensify collaboration between different SSH community stakeholders and to take an active role in promoting quality and impact of SSH within the European Research Area and beyond. It will enhance mutual interaction, further explore synergies and expertise, and support sharing of know-how in all areas of common interest.

In particular, it will:

- Maximise support to the SSH research communities and optimise the use of resources by sharing relevant developments and results.
- Identify common challenges affecting the SSH domain and collectively develop responses to these challenges.
- Support joint visibility and branding in the area of SSH.

¹ The European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) is a specific legal form that facilitates the establishment and operation of Research Infrastructures with European interest. ERICs carry out research programmes and projects and represent added value in the development of the European Research Area (ERA) and significant improvement in the SSH field with effective access granted to the European research community in accordance with the rules established in the statutes. ERICs actively contribute to the mobility of knowledge and/or researchers within the ERA, as well as to the dissemination and optimisation of the scientific results.

SSHOC, "Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud", has received funding from the EU Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (2014-2020) 101020-INFRAEOSC-04-2018, under the agreement No. 823782

Memorandum of Understanding for SSH Open Cluster

- all ERICs signed, committed
- CESSDA coordinating currently
- **maintaining** SSHOC results (SSH Marketplace SLA signed)
- TRUST among partners and communities
- **access to and overview of all results & stakeholders**
- providing further access to new members
- making sure the **community lives** long after the project

CESSDA Agenda 21-22

- TASK 1 - Events
- TASK 2 - Journal Outreach
- TASK 3 - DAG & DMEG

**Pillar 1
Training**

- TASK 1 - Metadata Aggregator
- TASK 2 - CDC upgrade
- TASK 3 - Data access upgrade
- TASK 4 - Dataverse business plan

**Pillar 2
Tools**

cessda
eric

Coordinating

- Cross pillar - Resource Directory

**Pillar 3
Widening
& Outreach**

**Pillar 4
Trust**

- TASK 1 - European Coverage
- TASK 2 - Researchers needs survey

- TASK 1 - Trust Activities

CESSDA EC projects

Participating

ERIC Forum

INFRASUPP-2018

RltrainPlus

INFRASUPP-2020

SSHOC

InfraEOSC-04

COORDINATE

INFRAIA-02-2020

EURhisFIRM

INFRADEV-2017

BY-COVID

INFRA-2021

HumMingBird

MIGRATION-2019

Building the

**EUROPEAN OPEN
SCIENCE CLOUD**

EOSC Future

InfraEOSC-03

RltrainPlus

INFRASUPP-2020

EOSC Nordic

InfraEOSC-05b

FAIRsFAIR

InfraEOSC-05c

EOSC Enhance

InfraEOSC-06

EOSC Hub

Einfra-12-2017

TRIPLE

InfraEOSC-02

EGI-ACE

InfraEOSC-07

European Open Science Cloud

- Infrastructure projects aligning European initiatives
- Federated structure with a system of systems
- Technical alignment for interoperability
- Services applicable to any research domain
- Catalogue of high quality services
- Support & Frameworks

Developed through

- EOSC Enhance (12/2019-11/2021)
- EOSC Future (04/2021-09/2023)

<https://eosc-portal.eu/>

Domain specific portals

SSH Open Marketplace

- Tools & services
- Training materials
- Workflows
- Supported by data and publications

GoTriple

- Scholarly communication & Open Science
- literature, data, projects and researcher profiles
- Connected to domain specific and generic catalogues

Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace

Discover new and contextualised resources for your research in Social Sciences and Humanities: tools, services, training materials, workflows and datasets. [Read more...](#)

The interconnected portal landscape

Finding data, tools, publications and more

- Different platforms
- Different purposes
- All interoperable
- Metadata exchange
- Common standards

There is still work to do

- Interconnection
- Synchronisation
- User guidance

**EUROPEAN OPEN
SCIENCE CLOUD**

**SSH Open
Marketplace**

Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace

GoTriple

Discovery service for the social sciences and humanities

cessda
DC Data Catalogue

To learn more, we invite you to attend:

Thursday, 9 June 2022

Partnerships and collaborations

10:00-12:00

Panel 3: Training as grounds for collaboration across disciplinary boundaries

Data literacy

13:30-15:00

Session E1: Using, managing and sharing vocabularies: SSH Vocabulary Commons

17:00-18:00

Posters

- **GoTriple Discovery Platform for Social Sciences and Humanities**

Friday, 10 June 2022

Partnerships and collaborations

11:00-12:30

Session H1: (Virtual) - Secure Data Facility Professionals Networks – what's in it for your TRE?

European RIs & advancing the Digital Future of Europe

Ivana Ilijasic Versic

Irena Vipavc Brvar

 cessda.eu

 @CESSDA_Data

CESSDA consortium

SSH domain

European Strategic Forum for Research Infrastructures - the Roadmap

THEMATIC AREAS

DATA, COMPUTING & DIGITAL
RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

ENERGY

ENVIRONMENT

HEALTH & FOOD

PHYSICAL SCIENCES & ENGINEERING

SOCIAL & CULTURAL INNOVATION

European Open Science Cloud and more

Europe strong history in the implementation of RIs

- **55 RI** from ESFRI Roadmap budget of **2B€/year**
- More than **1000 RI** receive national or European support
Budget:
FP7: Total **1.7 B€**
H2020: Total **2.5 B€**
- About **300k€/project** on average are devoted **to** training activities, but this results in a **scattered and fragmented** training context.
- The current management development programmes offered by universities and Business Schools **do not tackle the specific needs of RI and CF.**

The management of RIs and CFs has become a central issue to ensure an efficient interface with stakeholders as well as funding and political institutions.

Source: Lavitrano, M. (2022): RITrainPlus. Driving Excellence for Research Infrastructures and Core Facilities. (ritrainplus.eu)

RIttrainPlus aims to meet the needs

Source: RIttrainPlus (2022). About RiTrainPlus . (ritrainplus.eu)

ERA Policy Agenda: Research Infrastructures

Action 8 - Strengthen sustainability, accessibility and resilience of research infrastructures in the ERA

Expected impact

- Strengthened research infrastructure **services**, better adapted to user needs
- **Sustainability** of European research infrastructures (system as a whole)
- Better **accessibility** of European research infrastructures and their services to users across the EU, including through the EOSC
- Stronger **engagement of stakeholders** in research infrastructures activities
- Identification of opportunities for research infrastructure **clustering**
- Enhanced **impact on society**, skills and talents;
-

Source: Sobczak, D. (2022) Training and carriers of RI managers and operators in the context of the ERA Policy Agenda (ritrainplus.eu)

To learn more, we invite you to attend:

Wednesday, 8 June 2022

Partnerships and collaborations

17:00-18:30 PM

CESSDA special session. Developing Data Archives: Challenges of the Changing Environment

Thursday, 9 June 2022

Session F2: Partnerships and collaborations

15:30-17:00

SND – a Swedish national collaboration

Friday, 10 June 2022

Data Services of the future

13:30-15:00

Panel 8: Pan-European Research Data Infrastructure: Challenges of the Changing Environment

Go to www.menti.com
and use the code
4343 9685

Thank you!

Feel free to contact us at:

Ivana Ilijasic Versic, CESSDA ERIC MO (ivana.versic@cessda.eu)

Vanja Komljenovic, CESSDA ERIC MO (vanja.komljenovic@cessda.eu)

Dimitra Kondyli, EKKE (dkondyli@ekke.gr)

Martina Drascic Capar, CESSDA ERIC MO (martina.drascic@cessda.eu)

Irena Vipavc Brvar, UL-ADP (irena.Vipavc@fdv.uni-lj.si)

Carsten Thiel, CESSDA ERIC MO (carsten.thiel@cessda.eu)